

Legends to the supplementary figures.

Supplementary figure 1. Representation of sample types in the studied cohort. Purity assessment by flow cytometry of monocytes (A) and neutrophils (B) isolated using positive immunomagnetic isolation and negative immunomagnetic enrichment, respectively. In each panel, the leftmost plot is the unlabeled fraction and the four plots to the right are from separate representative isolations fluorescently tagged monocytes (CD36-APC) and neutrophils (CD16-PE and CD66b-FITC). (C) Principal component analysis for all genes in all samples analyzed from all diagnostic groups. (M: monocytes (green), N: neutrophils (orange) and WB: whole blood (brown)). Ellipsoids represent 2 standard deviations from the centroid.

Supplementary figure 2. Unsupervised Hierarchical Clustering of the ICH DEGs in (A) monocytes and (B) neutrophils. Subjects are in rows, DEGs are in columns. Red – high expression, green – low expression. Time since onset of symptoms is displayed for all cases (Time (h)). ICH: intracerebral hemorrhage, VRFC: vascular risk factor controls, DEGs: differentially expressed genes.

Supplementary figure 3. Unsupervised Hierarchical Clustering of the IS DEGs in (A) monocytes and (B) neutrophils. Subjects are in rows, DEGs are in columns. Red – high expression, green – low expression. rtPA administration is displayed for all cases (Yes – magenta, No - white). IS: ischemic stroke, VRFC: vascular risk factor controls, DEGs: differentially expressed genes.

Supplementary figure 4. Top 10 canonical pathways for IS and ICH cases that are exclusively over-represented (Fisher's p-value < 0.05) in (A) monocytes and (B) neutrophils. The asterisk depicts pathways with Benjamini-Hochberg corrected p-value < 0.05. In the plot, orange bars indicate predicted activation of the pathway, blue bars show predicted inhibition, white – no direction can be predicted, and grey depicts no prediction can be performed. The shades for every colored cell represent z-scores values. Arrows indicate predicted significant activation ($z \geq 2$, up arrow) or significant inhibition ($z \leq -2$, down arrow) of the pathway. The vertical orange line marks the $-\log(p\text{-value}) > 1.3$ threshold.

Supplementary figure 5. Upstream regulators predicted to drive the IS and ICH response in (A) monocytes, (B) neutrophils and (C) whole blood with an overlap p-value < 0.05. Asterisk depicts Benjamini-Hochberg corrected p-value < 0.05. Orange cells indicate predicted activation of the pathway, blue show predicted inhibition, white – no direction can be predicted, and grey depicts no prediction can be performed. The shades for every colored cell represent z-scores values. Arrows indicate predicted significant activation ($z \geq 2$, up arrow) or significant inhibition ($z \leq -2$, down arrow) of the pathway. Abbreviations: lig – ligand; r - receptor; reg – regulator; transmem - transmembrane.

Supplementary figure 6. Upstream transcriptional regulators predicted to drive the IS cause profiles. Top predicted regulators (p-value < 0.05) unique to each IS etiology ((A)CE: cardioembolic, (B) LV: large vessel and (C) SV: small vessel stroke) in all the sample types analyzed (M, monocytes; N, neutrophils and WB, whole blood) are displayed together with their predicted status. (D) heatmap of the top 10 common upstream regulators in the three sample types. Orange cells indicate predicted activation of the pathway, blue ones show predicted inhibition, white cells– no direction can be predicted. The shades for every colored cell represent z-scores values. Arrows represent the direction of a significantly activated ($z \geq 2$, up arrow); or significantly inhibited ($z \leq -2$, down arrow) upstream regulator. Asterisk represents Benjamini-Hochberg corrected p-value < 0.05. Abbreviations: lig – ligand; r - receptor; reg – regulator; transmem - transmembrane.

Supplementary figure 7. Upstream transcriptional regulators predicted to drive the IS cause profiles. On the left for each cell type (A) monocytes and (B) neutrophils) - Venn diagrams show the number of significant upstream regulators and the top 10 (Fisher's p-value < 0.05) predicted regulators unique to each IS etiology (CE: cardioembolic, LV: large vessel and SV: small vessel stroke). On the right, the top 10 common regulators across IS etiologies. In the heatmaps, shades represent z-scores values. Orange cells indicate predicted activation of the pathway, blue ones show predicted inhibition, white cells– no direction can be predicted. Arrows indicate predicted significant activation ($z \geq 2$, up arrow) or significant inhibition ($z \leq -2$, down arrow) of the pathway. Asterisk represents Benjamini-Hochberg corrected p-value < 0.05. Abbreviations: r - receptor; reg - regulator.